

Wa-module

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Abstract.

M.A.Hassin and A.B.Hussien introduced the following concept: (a, H) is called a ring over G if H is a subgroup of group G and $a \in G$ and a has finite order or infinite order, we called the ring $(w_a, +, \cdot)$; (a, H) Ring over G where

$$w_a = \{ a^m H a^n, m, n \in \mathbb{Z}, a \in G \setminus H \}$$

with two binary operations $+$ and \cdot . Such that $\forall a^{m_1} H a^{n_1}, a^{m_2} H a^{n_2} \in w_a, m_1, m_2, n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{Z}$

$$1- a^{m_1} H a^{n_1} + a^{m_2} H a^{n_2} = a^{m_1+m_2} H a^{n_1+n_2} .$$

$$2- a^{m_1} H a^{n_1} \cdot a^{m_2} H a^{n_2} = a^{m_1+m_2} H a^{n_1+n_2} .$$

In [4], $(w_a, +, \cdot)$ is commutative ring with unity aHa these lead us to give the definition of w_a -module define on the ring \mathbb{R} which is for any commutative ring with unity element.

The main purpose of this work is to give definition of w_a -module and some properties of W_a module many new and useful results are

Obtain about this concept, and we illustrate that by examples

Key words: injective module; Homomorphism; R-balanced.

Introduction :

The concept of module is very important in algebra [2], [3]. We give a definition of w_a -module, where R is a commutative ring with unity. In this work, we define a quotient module of this module, homomorphism and injective module of this module.

1- Wa-module

In this section we introduce the concept of w_a -module where R is an abelian group ring with identity, and G is an abelian group and H is a subgroup of G , then we can give a new definition.

Definition:(1-1)

Let R be a commutative ring with unity $1R$. An abelian group $(w_a, +)$ is called a left R -module if there exist a map $\varphi: R \times w_a \rightarrow w_a$ with

$\varphi (r,a^m H a^n)=a^m r H a^n$ satisfies the following:

- 1- $(r_1+r_2)(a^m H a^n)=a^m r_1 H a^n+a^m r_2 H a^n$
- 2- $r(a^m_1 H a^n_1+a^m_2 H a^n_2)=a^m_1 r H a^n_1+a^m_2 r H a^n_2$
- 3- $(r_1 r_2)a^m H a^n=r_1 (r_2 a^m H a^n)$
- 4- $1_R .a^m H a^n=a^m H a^n \forall r,r_1,r_2 \in R, \forall a^m H a^n, a^m_1 H a^n_1, a^m_2 H a^n_2 \in W_a$

To satisfy that.

$$1-(r_1+r_2)(a^m H a^n)=a^m (r_1+r_2) H a^n$$

$$=a^m (r_1 H+r_2 H) a^n$$

$$=a^m r_1 H a^n+a^m r_2 H a^n$$

$$2-r(a^m_1 H a^n_1+a^m_2 H a^n_2)=r(a^m_1+a^m_2) H a^n_1+a^n_2$$

$$=a^m_1+a^m_2 r H a^n_1+a^n_2$$

$$=a^m_1 r H a^n_1+a^m_2 r H a^n_2$$

$$3-(r_1 r_2)a^m H a^n=a^m (r_1 r_2) H a^n$$

$$=r_1 (a^m r_2 H a^n)$$

$$=r_1 (r_2 a^m H a^n)$$

$$4-1.a^m H a^n=a^m 1 H a^n=a^m H a^n$$

Note (1-2)

If R is a commutative ring then every left R-module can be considered as a right R-module

Example (1-3) :

1- Let $G=\mathbb{R}$, $H=2\mathbb{Z}$ & $\mathbf{R} = \mathbb{R}$ then w_a -module is

$$\{ a^m (2\mathbb{Z}) a^n ; m,n \in \mathbb{Z}, a \in 2\mathbb{Z} \}$$

identity element is (2) since $\forall x \in M$

$$x = a^m (2\mathbb{Z}) a^n \text{ such that } x+I = x \text{ where } I= a^0 (2\mathbb{Z}) a^0$$

so \mathbb{R} is w_a - module

2- \mathbb{Z} is not W_a - module since $a^m \notin \mathbb{Z}$ if $m = \mathbb{Z}$

Theorem (1.4)

Let N be an non empty subset of W_a such that $N=\{a^m H; a \notin H, H$ subgroup of $G, a \in G\}$

Then $(N,+)$ sub-module of $(W_a,+)$

Proof :

Let $x = a^{m_1}H \in N$, $y = a^{m_2}H \in N$

$$x+y = a^{m_1}H + a^{m_2}H$$

$$x+y = a^{m_1+m_2}H \in N$$

So $x+y \in N$

Let $r \in R, \forall x \in N; x = a^m H$

So $rx = r(a^m H) = a^m(rH); a^m \notin rH$

$\therefore rx \in N$ implies that N is a sub-module of W_a

Remark (1.5):

1- Every sub-module of W_a -module is W_a -module

2- Since $(W_a, +)$ is abelian group in [4], and we prove $(N, +)$ submodule of $(M, +)$ for each $N \neq \emptyset$ so $(N, +)$ is normal submodule of $(M, +)$, by definition of normal submodule in [5]

We can give the definition

Definition (1.6) : Quotient module

Let M be W_a -module and N be normal submodule of M then

$$M/N = \{x+N; x \in M\} = \{a^m H a^n + N; m, n \in \mathbb{Z}; a \in G/H\}$$

$$= \{a^m H a^n + a^k H; m, n, k \in \mathbb{Z}, a \in G/H\}$$

$$= \{a^{m+k} H a^n; m, n, k \in \mathbb{Z}, a \in G/H\}$$

To prove M/N is W_a -module we give the theorem.

Theorem (1.7) :

Let M be W_a -module, N be normal submodule of then M/N is W_a -module.

Proof :

We must prove $(M/N, \oplus)$ is abelian group

1 - \oplus closed

$\forall x_1, x_2 \in M/N$ to prove $x_1 + x_2 \in M/N$

Let $x_1 = a^{m_1} H a^{n_1} + N; m_1, n_1, k \in \mathbb{Z}$

$$= a^{m_1+k} H a^{n_1} \in M/N$$

Let $x_2 = a^{m_2} H a^{n_2} + N = a^{m_2} H a^{n_2} + a^k H; m_2, n_2, k \in \mathbb{Z}$

$$= a^{m_2+k} H a^{n_2} \in M/N$$

$$\begin{aligned}x_1+x_2 &= a^{m_1+k} Ha^{n_1} + a^{m_2+k} Ha^{n_2} \\ &= a^{m_1+k+m_2+k} Ha^{n_1+n_2} \\ &= a^w Ha^n; w = m_1+k+m_2+k \in \mathbb{Z}, n = n_1+n_2 \in \mathbb{Z}\end{aligned}$$

$$x_1, x_2 \in M/N$$

So \oplus is closed

2- \oplus is associative since + is associative on \mathbb{Z}

3- identity of M/N is $H+N = N$ since

$$\begin{aligned}H &= a^0 Ha^0 \quad \& \quad N = a^n H \text{ so } H+N = (a^0 Ha^0 \oplus a^n H) \\ &= a^n H = N\end{aligned}$$

So $\forall (x+N) \in M/N$ where $x \in M$ implies

$$\text{That } (x+N) \oplus N = x+N \quad \forall x \in M$$

4- inverse : $\forall x+N \in M/N$ implies

$$-x+N \in M/N; \quad -x = a^{-m} Ha^{-n}$$

$$(x+N) \oplus (-x+N) = (x+(-x))+N$$

$$= (a^m Ha^n + a^{-m} Ha^{-n})+N$$

$$= (a^{m-m} Ha^{n-n})+N$$

$$= a^0 Ha^0 + N$$

$$= H+N = N$$

5-abelian : $\forall x_1+N, x_2+N \in M/N \quad \forall x_1, x_2 \in M$

$$(x_1+N) \oplus (x_2+N) = (x_1+x_2) + N$$

$$= (x_2+x_1) + N$$

$$= (x_2+N) \oplus (x_1+N) \quad |$$

So $(M/N, \oplus)$ is abelian group

Let R be any commutative ring with the unity 1_R

$$\text{Let } \phi: R \times M/N \rightarrow M/N \text{ s.t } \phi(r, x+N) = a^{m+k} r H a^n$$

Similarly we can prove

$$6- r(x_1+x_2)+N = rx_1 + rx_2 + N \quad \forall r \in R, x_1, x_2 \in M$$

$$7- \text{to prove } (r_1+r_2)(x+N) = r_1x + N + r_2x + N$$

$\forall r_1, r_2 \in R, x \in M$

$$8- r_1 r_2 (x_2 + N) = r_1 (r_2 (X + N))$$

So $M \setminus N$ is wa-module

2- Homomorphism and injective module:

In this section we give the definition of homomorphism map on wa-module .in [4] we can see the definition of homomorphism module.

Definition 2.1 :

Let N, M be two wa-modules then $\varphi: M \rightarrow N$ can define by $\varphi(a^m H a^n) = a^{\varphi(m)} H a^{\varphi(n)}$; $m, n \in Z$

Definition(2.2): (Homomorphism on W_a -module)

Let M, N be two W_a -modules, then mapping $\varphi : M \rightarrow N$ is homomorphism if

$$\varphi(a^m H a^n + a^{m_1} H a^{n_1}) = \varphi(a^m H a^n) + \varphi(a^{m_1} H a^{n_1}) ; m, n, m_1, n_1 \in Z$$

$$2- \varphi(r a^m H a^n) = r \varphi(a^m H a^n) ; m, n \in Z, r \in R$$

Thus we have the following theorem.

Theorem (2.3): Let $\varphi : M \rightarrow K$ be homomorphism such that M, K be two W_a -module then if N be W_a -submodule of M then $\varphi(N)$ is wa-submodule of K .

Proof:

Let $x, y \in \varphi(N)$, $a, b \in N, m, n \in Z$

$$x = \varphi(c); \text{ so } c = a^m H$$

$$y = \varphi(b); \text{ } b = a^n H$$

$$x = \varphi(a^m H)$$

$$y = \varphi(a^n H)$$

$$x + y = \varphi(a^m H) + \varphi(a^n H) = a^{\varphi(m)} H + a^{\varphi(n)} H$$

$$= a^{\varphi(m) + \varphi(n)} H$$

$$= a^{\varphi(m+n)} H \in \varphi(N)$$

2- let $r \in R, x \in \varphi(N)$ to prove $rx \in \varphi(N), x \in \varphi(N)$ so

$$x = \varphi(b); b \in N$$

$$\text{so } b = a^m H ; m \in Z$$

$$\text{so } x = \varphi(a^m H) = a$$

$$\begin{aligned} rX &= r \otimes (a^m H) \\ &= \otimes [(a^m (rH))] \\ &= a^{\otimes(m)}(rH) \in \otimes (N) \end{aligned}$$

$\therefore \otimes (N)$ is submodule of K

Definition (2-4):

Let $f : M \rightarrow M$ be homomorphism where M be wa- module

$$\text{Ker } f = \{ x \in M ; \emptyset (a^m H a^n) = H \}$$

$$= \{ a \in M ; a^{\otimes(m)} H a^{\otimes(n)} ; m, n \in \mathbb{Z} \}$$

$$= \{ a \in M ; a \emptyset(m) H = H a \emptyset^{-n} ; m, n \in \mathbb{Z} \}$$

We can find the relation between wa-module and injective module where a module is called injective if for each monomorphism $f : A \rightarrow B$ where A, B are two module and for each homomorphism $g : A \rightarrow M$ there exist a homomorphism $h : B \rightarrow M$ s.t $h \circ f = g$ see [5]

$$h \circ f = g$$

Theorem 2.5

If M is R – wa – module then M is injective module

Proof

Let $f : A \rightarrow A \times A$; A be any module such that $f(a) = (a, a)$

f is monomorphism since f is I-I

if $f(a_1) = f(a_2)$ for each $a_1, a_2 \in A$

$$\rightarrow (a_1, a_1) = (a_2, a_2)$$

$$\rightarrow a_1 = a_2$$

so f is I-I

$$A \xrightarrow{f} A \times A$$

$g \exists h$

$hof = M \quad M$

$$1- f(a_1+a_2) = (a_1+a_2, a_1+a_2) \forall a_1, a_2 \in A$$

$$= (a_1, a_1) + (a_2, a_2)$$

$$= f(a_1) + f(a_2)$$

$$2- f(ra) = (ra, ra)$$

$$= r(a, a) = rf(a)$$

Then f is homomorphism so f is monomorphism

Let there exist homomorphism function

$$g: A \rightarrow M ; g(a) = aHa$$

$$1- g(a_1+a_2) = (a_1+a_2)H(a_1+a_2) \forall a_1, a_2 \in A$$

$$= a_1Ha_1 + a_2Ha_2$$

$$= g(a_1) + g(a_2)$$

$$g(ra) = a(rH)a ; r \in R, a \in A$$

$$= r(aHa)$$

$$= r g(a)$$

So g is homomorphism, there exist homomorphism $h : A \times A \rightarrow M ; h((a, a)) = aHa$

$$1- h(a_1, a_1) + h(a_2, a_2) = h((a_1+a_2, a_1+a_2))$$

$$= (a_1+a_2)H(a_1+a_2)$$

$$= a_1Ha_1 + a_2Ha_2$$

$$= h(a_1) + h(a_2)$$

$$2- h(r(a_1, a_1)) = h(ra_1, ra_2)$$

$$= a_1(rh)a_2$$

$$= r(a_1Ha_2) = r h(a_1)$$

$$= rh(a_1)$$

∴ h is homomorphism to prove hof (a) =g(a) h of

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ho } f(a) &= h(f(a)) \\ &= h((a,a)) = aHa \end{aligned}$$

h of (a) =g(a)

then M is injective

but the converse of theorem is not true for example :

Q as z-module is injective since by theorem an abelian group if Z is injective module [5] but Q is not Z – wa-module.

3- R-balanced and wa- module

In this section we study the relation between R – balanced and wa- module

Definition (3.1) R – balanced [1] Let M,N be two module over ring R and let G be abelian group ,a function $f:MXN \rightarrow G$ is said to be R-balanced in case for all $m_1, m_2 \in M, n_1, n_2 \in N$ and $r \in R$

- 1- $f(m_1+m_2, n) = f(m_1, n) + f(m_2, n)$
- 2- $f(m, n_1+n_2) = f(m, n_1) + f(m, n_2)$
- 3- $f(mr, n) = f(m, rn)$

Theorem 3.2

Every function from wa-module to an abelian group is R – balanced

Proof:

Let M,N between wa-module and G be abelian group

Let the function $f: MXN \rightarrow G$; $f(a,b) = ab$

1- $f(m_1+m_2, n) = (m_1+m_2) n$; $m_1, m_2 \in M$, $n \in N$ let

$$m_1 = a^k Ha^w$$

$$m_2 = a^{k_1} Ha^{w_1}$$

$$n = a^{k_2} Ha^{w_2}; k_1, k_2, k, w, w_1, w_2 \in \mathbb{Z}$$

$$= (a^k Ha^w + a^{k_1} Ha^{w_1})(a^{k_2} Ha^{w_2})$$

$$= (a^{k+k_1} Ha^{w+w_1})(a^{k_2} Ha^{w_2})$$

$$= a^{(k+k_1)k_2} Ha^{(w+w_1)w_2}$$

$$= a^{kk_2+k_1k_2} Ha^{ww_2+w_1w_2}$$

$$= a^{kk_2} Ha^{ww_2} + a^{k_1k_2} Ha^{w_1w_2}$$

$$= (a^k H a^w)(a^{k_2} H a^{w_2}) + (a^{k_1} H a^{w_1})(a^{k_2} H a^{w_2})$$

$$= m_1 n + m_2 n$$

$$= f(m_1, n) + f(m_2, n)$$

2- to prove $f(m, n_1 + n_2) = f(m, n_1) + f(m, n_2)$ $f(m_1, n_1 + n_2) = m_1(n_1 + n_2)$; $m_1 = a^k H a^w, n_1 = a^{k_1} H a^{w_1}, n_2 = a^{k_2} H a^{w_2}$
; $k, k_1, k_2; w, w_1, w_2 \in \mathbb{Z}$

$$\begin{aligned} &= a^k H a^w \cdot (a^{k_1} H a^{w_1} + a^{k_2} H a^{w_2}) \\ &= a^k H a^w (a^{k_1+k_2} H a^{w_1+w_2}) \\ &= a^{k(k_1+k_2)} H a^{w(w_1+w_2)} \\ &= a^{kk_1+kk_2} H a^{ww_1+ww_2} \\ &= a^{kk_1} H a^{ww_1} + a^{kk_2} H a^{ww_2} \\ &= (a^k H a^w)(a^{k_1} H a^{w_1}) + (a^k H a^w)(a^{k_2} H a^{w_2}) \\ &= m n_1 + m n_2 \\ &= f(m_1, n_1) + f(m_1, n_2) \end{aligned}$$

3- to prove $f(mr, n) = f(m, rn)$ let $m = a^k H a^w, n = a^{k_1} H a^{w_1}$

$$\begin{aligned} f(mr, n) &= (mr)n \\ &= (a^k H a^w) r(a^{k_1} H a^{w_1}) \\ &= (a^k H a^w) (a^{k_1} (rH) a^{w_1}) \\ &= m (rn) \\ &= f(m, rn) \end{aligned}$$

So wa - module is R -balanced.

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المقاس من الخط wa

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م. منتهى عبد الرزاق و م . أحمدباقر قدما المفهوم الأتي يقال (a,H) انه حلقة اذا كان H زمرة جزئية من الزمرة G و $a \in G$ وله رتبة منتهية وغير منتهية . حيث نسمي الحلقة (wa,+,.) بالحلقة (a,H) على الزمرة G

$$Wa = \{a^m Ha^n ; m, n \in Z, a \in G \setminus H\}$$

مع عمليتين ثنائيتين + , . بحيث ان :-

$$1- a^{m_1} Ha^{n_1} + a^{m_2} Ha^{n_2} = a^{m_1+m_2} Ha^{n_1+n_2}$$

$$2- a^{m_1} Ha^{n_1} \cdot a^{m_2} Ha^{n_2} = a^{m_1 m_2} Ha^{n_1 n_2}$$

$$\square m_1, m_2, n_1, n_2 \in Z, a^{m_1} Ha^{n_1}, a^{m_2} Ha^{n_2} \in wa$$

وفي المصدر [4] تم برهان ان (wa,+,.) زمرة ابدالية مع عنصر محايد وهذه قادتنا الى تعريف wa-module على الحلقة R وهي مجموعة من الاعداد الحقيقية .

الهدف الرئيسي من هذا العمل ان نجد تعريف (wa-module) وبعض خواصه ولقد وجدنا مجموعة من النتائج المفيدة والجديدة حول هذا المفهوم واوضحنا المفاهيم بالأمثلة .